

Data submissions of the TR172 – (AC)³ project

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Abstract

This document lists all data publications created in the Transregional Collaborative Research Centre TR 172 – (AC)³ (see <http://www.ac3-tr.de>). The project started on 2016/01/01 and the current snapshot provides all data published until 2023/04/06. The data sets are ordered by date of publication.

Any citation of the research data below should reference the corresponding DOI of the data sets and not this document.

Data publications

Title	Authors	Date	Link
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2013-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2014-03-31	831324
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2013-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2014-03-31	831339
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2013-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2014-03-31	831329
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2013-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2014-03-31	831334
Basic and other measurements of radiation from the Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) Station Ny-Ålesund in the years 1992 to 2013, reference list of 253 datasets	Maturilli, Marion; Herber, Andreas; König-Langlo, Gert	2014-04-14	150000
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-20	845356
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-20	845351
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-20	845361
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845761
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845751
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845771
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845791
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845786
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845776
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845756
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845781
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2014-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-04-28	845766
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-10-23	854321

Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2015-10-26	854373
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-03)	Maturilli, Marion; Ritter, Christoph	2016-01-12	854326
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1994	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-03-27	845023
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1993	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-03-27	845022
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2009	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845333
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2004	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845328
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2008	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845332
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2001	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845325
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2007	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845331
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2005	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845329
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2003	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845327
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1997	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845320
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2014	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845338
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1999	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845322
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2012	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845336
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2013	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845337
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1996	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845319
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2000	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845324
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1998	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845321
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 1995	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845306
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2002	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845326
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2010	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845334
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2011	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845335
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2006	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-04-20	845330
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen, 1993-2014	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2016-07-11	845373
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863290
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863255
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863260
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863295
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863275

Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863265
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863270
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863280
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2015-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2016-07-22	863285
Global monthly mean chlorophyll a surface concentrations from August 2002 to April 2012 for diatoms, coccolithophores and cyanobacteria from PhytoDOAS algorithm version 3.3 applied to SCIAMACHY data, link to NetCDF files in ZIP archive	Bracher, Astrid; Dinter, Tilman; Wolanin, Aleksandra; Rozanov, Vladimir V; Losa, Svetlana N; Soppa, Mariana A	2017-01-06	870486
Column averaged dry-air mole fractions of CO ₂ and CH ₄ at Ny-Ålesund from 2012 to 2016	Buschmann, Matthias; Deutscher, Nicholas M; Palm, Mathias; Warneke, Thorsten; Weinzierl, Tine; Notholt, Justus	2017-02-13	872007
Global data sets of Chlorophyll a concentration for diatoms, coccolithophores (haptophytes) and cyanobacteria obtained from in situ observations and satellite retrievals	Losa, Svetlana N; Soppa, Mariana A; Dinter, Tilman; Wolanin, Aleksandra; Brewin, Robert J W; Bricaud, Annick; Oelker, Julia; Peeken, Ilka; Gentili, Bernard; Rozanov, Vladimir V; Bracher, Astrid	2017-03-03	873210
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873812
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873785
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873793
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873800
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873790
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873817
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873767
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873780
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873822
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873775
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873807
Basic and other measurements of radiation at station Ny-Ålesund (2016-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-03-22	873770
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-14, St.01)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-04-24	874795
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-14, St.03)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-04-24	874797
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-14, St.02)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-04-24	874796

Cloud optical thickness retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE during VERDI campaign 2012	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-04-24	874798
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-15, St.04)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-04-24	874799
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-16, St.06)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-02	874937
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-17, St.07)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-02	874939
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-15, St.05)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-02	874936
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-17, St.08)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-03	874970
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-17, St.10)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-03	874983
Cloud optical thickness (tau) retrieved from horizontal fields of reflected solar spectral radiance measured with AisaEAGLE (2015-05-17, St.09)	Schäfer, Michael; Bierwirth, Eike; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Werner, Frank; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-05-03	874982
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2015	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2017-05-15	875193
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen in 2016	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2017-05-15	875194
Homogenized radiosonde record at station Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen, 2015-2016	Maturilli, Marion; Kayser, Markus	2017-05-15	875196
Global chlorophyll a surface concentrations for diatoms, coccolithophores and cyanobacteria as the synergistic SynSenPFT product combined PhytoDOAS and OC-PFT for the period of time August 2002 - April 2012, links to NetCDF files	Losa, Svetlana N; Soppa, Mariana A; Dinter, Tilman; Wolanin, Aleksandra; Oelker, Julia; Bracher, Astrid	2017-06-01	875873
Global chlorophyll a concentrations for diatoms, haptophytes and prokaryotes obtained with the Diagnostic Pigment Analysis of HPLC data compiled from several databases and individual cruises	Soppa, Mariana A; Peeken, Ilka; Bracher, Astrid	2017-06-01	875879
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-08-18	879767
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-08-23	879822
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-08-23	879823
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-08-23	879820
Ceilometer cloud base height from station Ny-Ålesund from August 1992 to July 2017, reference list of 290 datasets	Maturilli, Marion; Herber, Andreas	2017-09-12	880300

High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-10-09	881622
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-10-09	881621
Cloud optical thickness, cloud particle effective radius, and effective snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral reflectivity measurements on 2012-05-17 (VERDI 2012) over the Beaufort Sea	Ehrlich, André; Bierwirth, Eike; Istomina, Larisa; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-11-14	882977
Cloud optical thickness, cloud particle effective radius, and effective snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral reflectivity measurements on 2012-04-29 (VERDI 2012) over the Beaufort Sea	Ehrlich, André; Bierwirth, Eike; Istomina, Larisa; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-11-14	882978
Cloud optical thickness, cloud particle effective radius, and effective snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral reflectivity measurements during VERDI 2012 over the Beaufort Sea	Ehrlich, André; Bierwirth, Eike; Istomina, Larisa; Wendisch, Manfred	2017-11-14	882979
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-12-04	883700
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2017-12-04	883703
Absorption line height and chl-a during POLARSTERN cruises PS93.2 and PS99.2 from underway spectrophotometry and discrete water samples	Liu, Yangyang; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Ramírez-Pérez, Marta; Dinter, Tilman; Steinmetz, Francois; Nöthig, Eva-Maria; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2018-01-26	885631
Absorption line height and chl-a during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.2 from underway spectrophotometry	Liu, Yangyang; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Ramírez-Pérez, Marta; Dinter, Tilman; Steinmetz, Francois; Nöthig, Eva-Maria; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2018-01-26	885630
Absorption line height, chl-a concentration and fraction of major phytoplankton groups on chl-a during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.2 from discrete samples	Liu, Yangyang; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Ramírez-Pérez, Marta; Dinter, Tilman; Steinmetz, Francois; Nöthig, Eva-Maria; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2018-01-29	885688
Absorption line height and chl-a during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2 from underway spectrophotometry	Liu, Yangyang; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Ramírez-Pérez, Marta; Dinter, Tilman; Steinmetz, Francois; Nöthig, Eva-Maria; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2018-01-29	885686
Absorption line height, chl-a concentration and fraction of major phytoplankton groups on chl-a during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2 from discrete samples	Liu, Yangyang; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Ramírez-Pérez, Marta; Dinter, Tilman; Steinmetz, Francois; Nöthig, Eva-Maria; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2018-01-29	885687
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2017-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-02-26	886871
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-02-26	886872
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703301101	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888129
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704021401	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888132
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704051702	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888135

Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704061801	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888136
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704051601	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888134
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704041501	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888133
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703280901	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888127
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703210602	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888124
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703240801	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888126
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704112201	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888140
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703311201	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888130
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704071901	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888137
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704102101	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888139
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704132401	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888142
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703200401	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888122
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 5 campaign ACLOUD_2017	Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Lüpkes, Christof; Crewell, Susanne; Mech, Mario	2018-04-09	888173
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703130201	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888120
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703220701	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888125
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703281002	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888128
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703210501	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888123
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704122301	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888141
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704082001	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888138
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703030101	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888119

Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704011301	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888131
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704152701	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888146
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704132502	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888143
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 5 campaign PAMARCMIP_2017	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888147
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1704142601	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888144
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2017_1703130302	Herber, Andreas	2018-04-09	888121
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 6 campaign ACLOUD_2017	Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Lüpkes, Christof; Crewell, Susanne; Mech, Mario	2018-04-10	888365
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1804021201	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890843
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803280902	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890840
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1804021302	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890844
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803230301	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890834
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1802280101	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890832
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803020201	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890833
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803270701	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890838
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1804031401	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890845
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803250401	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890835
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803301001	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890841
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803260602	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890837
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803311101	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890842
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803280801	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890839

Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1804041601	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890847
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1803260501	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890836
Links to master tracks in different resolutions from POLAR 5 flight PAMAR-CMIP_2018_1804031502	Herber, Andreas	2018-06-07	890846
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-06-19	891223
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-06-19	891222
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-06-19	891216
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-06-19	891224
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706262401	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891586
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706141701	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891582
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706252301	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891585
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during the ACLOUD campaign	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891588
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706081401	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891581
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1705230601	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891576
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1705311101	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891579
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706051301	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891580
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706182001	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891583
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1706202101	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891584
Aircraft measurements of up- and downward irradiances over Arctic sea ice during flight ACLOUD_P5_2017_1705291001	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2018-06-29	891578
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-09-21	894695
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-09-21	894698
Phytoplankton pigment concentration measured by HPLC during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2018-09-27	894860

Phytoplankton pigment concentration measured by HPLC during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2018-09-28	894872
Phytoplankton pigment concentration measured by HPLC during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2018-09-28	894874
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2018-10-02	894954
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements in winter 2016/2017, calibrated with GRUAN radiosounding product	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896481
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements 2015-2018	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896486
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements in winter 2016/2017, processed by Vaisala radiosounding product	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896482
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements in winter 2015/2016, processed by Vaisala radiosounding product	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896480
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements in winter 2015/2016, calibrated with GRUAN radiosounding product	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896477
Water vapour mixing ratio over Ny-Alesund from LiDAR measurements in winter 2017/2018, processed by Vaisala radiosounding product	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Ritter, Christoph	2018-12-04	896484
Spatial and temporal variability of broadband solar irradiance during POLARSTERN cruise PS106/1 Ice Floe Camp (June 4th-16th 2017)	Barrientos Velasco, Carola; Deneke, Hartwig; Macke, Andreas	2018-12-12	896710
Global marine chlorophyll-a fluorescence line height monthly 2003-2011 data from SCIAMACHY (netCDF files)	Wolanin, Aleksandra; Rozanov, Vladimir V; Dinter, Tilman; Noël, S; Vountas, Marco; Burrows, John Philipp; Bracher, Astrid	2019-01-09	897169
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-01-10	897225
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-01-10	897226
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-01-10	897229
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2018-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-01-10	897224
Phytoplankton pigment concentration estimated from underway AC-S particulate absorption data during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-06	898101
Phytoplankton pigment concentration estimated from underway AC-S particulate absorption data during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-06	898100
Phytoplankton pigment concentration estimated from underway AC-S particulate absorption data during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-06	898102

Spectral particulate absorption coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898121
Spectral particulate attenuation coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898122
Spectral particulate absorption coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898119
Phytoplankton pigment concentrations measured by HPLC and estimated from underway spectrophotometry, and the particulate absorption and attenuation spectra derived from underway spectrophotometry during POLARSTERN cruises PS93.2, PS99.2 and PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	894875
Spectral particulate attenuation coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898120
Spectral particulate absorption coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898117
Spectral particulate attenuation coefficients and their standard deviation derived from underway AC-S measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Boss, Emmanuel; Chase, Alison P; Xi, Hongyan; Zhang, Xiaodong; Röttgers, Rüdiger; Pan, Yanqun; Bracher, Astrid	2019-02-07	898118
AMSR2 ASI sea ice concentration data, Arctic, version 5.4 (NetCDF) (July 2012 - December 2019)	Melsheimer, Christian; Spreen, Gunnar	2019-02-14	898399
Cloud microphysical properties retrieved from ground-based remote sensing at Ny-Ålesund (10 June 2016 - 8 October 2018)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-02-18	898556
Meteorological observations during POLAR 5 campaign PAMARCMIP 2018	Herber, Andreas	2019-02-26	898788
Measurements of Ice Nucleating Particles in ice core samples from Lomonosovfonna (Svalbard) and Summit (Greenland)	Hartmann, Markus; Blunier, Thomas; Brügger, Sandra Olivia; Schmale, Julia; Schwikowski, Margit; Vogel, Alexander; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-05	899048
Measurements of ice nucleating particles in ice core samples from Summit (Greenland) with LINA	Hartmann, Markus; Blunier, Thomas; Brügger, Sandra Olivia; Schmale, Julia; Schwikowski, Margit; Vogel, Alexander; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-05	899045
Measurements of ice nucleating particles in ice core samples from Lomonosovfonna (Svalbard) with INDA	Hartmann, Markus; Blunier, Thomas; Brügger, Sandra Olivia; Schmale, Julia; Schwikowski, Margit; Vogel, Alexander; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-05	899046
Measurements of ice nucleating particles in ice core samples from Lomonosovfonna (Svalbard) with LINA	Hartmann, Markus; Blunier, Thomas; Brügger, Sandra Olivia; Schmale, Julia; Schwikowski, Margit; Vogel, Alexander; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-05	899047
Measurements of ice nucleating particles in ice core samples from Summit (Greenland) with INDA	Hartmann, Markus; Blunier, Thomas; Brügger, Sandra Olivia; Schmale, Julia; Schwikowski, Margit; Vogel, Alexander; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-05	899044

CDP, CIP and PIP In-situ arctic cloud microphysical properties observed during ACLOUD-AC3 campaign in June 2017	Dupuy, Regis; Jourdan, Olivier; Mioche, Guillaume; Gourbeyre, Christophe; Leroy, Delphine; Schwarzenböck, Alfons	2019-03-06	899074
Aircraft measurements of spectral solar up- and downward irradiances in the Arctic during the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-03-07	899177
Meteorological measurements at 2m during a PASCAL ice station on POLARSTERN cruise PS106/1	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger	2019-03-12	899230
Measurements on the 10m meteorological and turbulence mast during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger	2019-03-12	899233
Ultrasonic anemometer turbulence measurements at 10m during a PASCAL ice station on POLARSTERN cruise PS106/1	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger	2019-03-12	899232
Glucose, T50 and salinity in the surface micro-layer and bulk water samples from the Arctic during POLARSTERN cruise PS106 (2017)	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Hartmann, Markus; Bracher, Astrid; Wiegmann, Sonja; Stratmann, Frank; Herrmann, Hartmut	2019-03-13	899258
Phytoplankton pigment concentration and phytoplankton groups measured on water samples obtained during POLARSTERN cruise PS106 in the Arctic Ocean	Bracher, Astrid	2019-03-14	899284
OCEANET-ATMOSPHERE PollyXT measurements during POLARSTERN cruise PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engemann, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2019-03-18	899458
Raw data of POLAR 5 campaign PAMARCMIP 2018	Herber, Andreas; Bozem, Heiko; Hendricks, Stefan; Holzinger, Rupert; Jäkel, Evelyn; Koike, Makoto; Neuber, Roland; Petzold, Andreas; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-21	899508
Airborne radar reflectivity and brightness temperature measurements with POLAR 5 during ACLOUD in May and June 2017	Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Mech, Mario	2019-03-22	899565
Measurements of Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN) concentrations in the Arctic during Polarstern cruise PS106	Hartmann, Markus; Henning, Silvia; Herenz, Paul; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-22	899570
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803280801 and flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803280902	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899629
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803311101	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899631
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803230301	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899625
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1804031401 and flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1804031502	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899633
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803301001	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899630
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1804021201	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899632
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803260501	Hartmann, Markus; Jentsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899627

Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803250401	Hartmann, Markus; Jentzsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899626
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803270701	Hartmann, Markus; Jentzsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899628
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1804041601	Hartmann, Markus; Jentzsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899634
Annual concentrations of ice nucleating particles at Arctic station Alert	Wex, Heike; Huang, Lin; Sheesley, Rebecca; Bossi, Rossana; Traversi, Rita	2019-03-26	899656
Airborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during PAMARCMiP 2018	Hartmann, Markus; Jentzsch, Conrad; Wex, Heike; Stratmann, Frank	2019-03-26	899635
Annual concentrations of ice nucleating particles at different Arctic stations	Wex, Heike; Huang, Lin; Sheesley, Rebecca; Bossi, Rossana; Traversi, Rita	2019-03-27	899701
Annual concentrations of ice nucleating particles at Arctic station Barrow/Utqiagvik	Wex, Heike; Huang, Lin; Sheesley, Rebecca; Bossi, Rossana; Traversi, Rita	2019-03-27	899698
Annual concentrations of ice nucleating particles at Arctic station Ny-Ålesund	Wex, Heike; Huang, Lin; Sheesley, Rebecca; Bossi, Rossana; Traversi, Rita	2019-03-27	899696
Annual concentrations of ice nucleating particles at Arctic station Villum	Wex, Heike; Huang, Lin; Sheesley, Rebecca; Bossi, Rossana; Traversi, Rita	2019-03-27	899700
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence and radiation during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-03-29	899803
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171901	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899951
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899936
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899927
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899924
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899918
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899923
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899922
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899919
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262401 (01)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899959
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262401 (02)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899960
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232201 (07)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899956
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899937

Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899921
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during the ACLOUD campaign	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899962
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899925
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899926
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232201 (06)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899955
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202101 (03)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899954
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202101 (01)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899953
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-04-03	899966
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161801	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899949
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899929
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706182001	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899952
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899932
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899928
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021201 (04)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899945
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270801	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899940
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021201 (03)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899944
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899933
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-04-03	899967
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899934
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-04-03	899965
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899917

Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706051301	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899946
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206.ACLOUD.2017.1705310901	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899920
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706081401	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899947
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1705291001 (03)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899942
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706202001	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899931
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706252301 (01)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899957
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706021201 (01)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899943
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1705250701	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899939
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706131601	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899948
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706252301 (02)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899958
Aircraft measurements of refractory black carbon in the Arctic during flight P6.206.ACLOUD.2017.1706181901	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-03	899930
Cloud top altitudes observed with airborne lidar during flight P5.206.ACLOUD.2017.1705291001 (02)	Neuber, Roland; Schmidt, Lukas Valentin; Ritter, Christoph; Mech, Mario	2019-04-03	899941
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170609.0932.1008)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-04	900096
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170609.0847.0927)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-04	900099
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170608.1405.1549)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900121
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170608.1308.1343)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900118
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170605.1112.1445)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900119
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170608.0856.1235)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900122
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170606.0913.1200)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900124
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic.20170607.0928.1059)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900120

Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic_20170612.0934.1149)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-05	900123
Sonic anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Sonic_20170614.0838.1140)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900200
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180324.1530.1611)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900222
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180324.1346.1453)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900221
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180326.1108.1236)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900225
Hotwire anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Hotwire_20170611.1301.1414)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900209
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180330.0258.0726)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900233
Hotwire anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Hotwire_20170607.1315.1443)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900211
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence and radiation during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP in March/ April 2018	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900240
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180329.2240.0014)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900232
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180329.1336.1718)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900230
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180404.1025.1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900239
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180322.1542.1652)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900219
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180403.1657.2044)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900238
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180401.1034.1151)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900235
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_StdMeteo_20180322.1156.1353)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900218

Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180321.1737.1937)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900217
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180329.1752.2216)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900231
Meteorological measurements by dropsondes released from POLAR 5 during ACLOUD 2017	Ehrlich, André; Stapf, Johannes; Lüpkes, Christof; Mech, Mario; Crewell, Susanne; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-04-08	900204
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180328.1123.1508)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900228
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180325.1313.1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900223
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180325.1537.1614)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900224
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180330.0806.0958)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900234
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180402.1005.1232)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900237
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180401.1248.1544)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900236
Hotwire anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon.Hotwire_20170610.1418.1808)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900212
Hotwire anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon.Hotwire_20170608.1359.1552)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900213
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180323.1217.1533)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900220
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180327.1106.1556)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900227
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180329.1202.1301)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900229
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.StdMeteo_20180326.1310.1709)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-08	900226
Hotwire anemometer measurements during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon.Hotwire_20170610.1040.1116)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-04-08	900208

SID-3 1Hz size distribution of cloud particles during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Schnaiter, Martin; Järvinen, Emma	2019-04-09	900261
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900333
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900339
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.20180321_1737_1937)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-10	900276
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900322
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900337
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900331
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900340
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900323
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.20180330_0258_0726)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-10	900321
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900330
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900338
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900326
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900332
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900327
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900328

Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900341
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180322_1542_1652)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-10	900281
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900324
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900334
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900329
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900335
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900325
Aircraft measurements of aerosol size distribution in the Arctic during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001 of the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Zanatta, Marco; Herber, Andreas	2019-04-10	900336
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180403_1657_2044)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-11	900374
SID-3 analysis results for 2D scattering patterns during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Schnaiter, Martin; Järvinen, Emma	2019-04-11	900380
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180328_1123_1508)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-11	900376
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900392
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900398
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900396
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900394

Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900393
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900395
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during the ACLOUD campaign in May and June 2017	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900403
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-12	900388
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900417
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900415
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900422
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.20180325_1313_1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-15	900438
Aircraft measurements of broadband irradiance during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-04-15	900442
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900421
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900419
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon.20180329_1336_1718)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-15	900443

Lidar aerosol properties over Ny-Alesund during May-June 2017	Ritter, Christoph	2019-04-15	900423
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180324_1346_1453)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-15	900424
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180330_0806_0958)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-15	900444
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900414
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900413
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900412
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900416
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-15	900420
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1336_1718, second part)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-16	900451
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-23	900507
Airborne in-situ measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient, aerosol particle number concentration and size distribution of cloud particle residuals and ambient aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301	Mertes, Stephan; Kästner, Udo; Macke, Andreas	2019-04-23	900506
Airborne measurements during POLAR 5 campaign ACLOUD in 2017 with links to raw data files	Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Lüpkes, Christof; Crewell, Susanne; Chechin, Dmitry; Hartmann, Jörg; Herber, Andreas; Jäkel, Evelyn; Mech, Mario; Neuber, Roland; Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Schäfer, Michael; Stapf, Johannes	2019-04-23	900501

Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180403_1657_2044)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-24	900616
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180330_0258_0726)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-25	900699
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1336_1718)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-25	900705
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1752_2216)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-04-25	900710
High resolution aircraft measurements of wind and temperature during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Hartmann, Jörg; Lüpkes, Christof; Chechin, Dmitry	2019-04-30	900880
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180404_1025_1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900930
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180326_1310_1709)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900920
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180323_1217_1533)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900921
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180402_1005_1232)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900927
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180401_1248_1544)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900923
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_2240_0014)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900925
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180327_1106_1556)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2019-05-02	900922
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901031
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901034
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901045
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901038
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901035
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901041

Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901044
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901036
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901046
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901028
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901032
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901043
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901040
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901033
Radiance fields of clouds and the Arctic surface measured by a digital camera during ACLOUD 2017	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André	2019-05-06	901024
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901042
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901047
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901037
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901030
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901039
Aircraft-based measurement of particle size and chemical composition for individual aerosol particles during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-06	901029

Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901142
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901133
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901136
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901134
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901148
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during ACLOUD 2017	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901149
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901145
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901135
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901132
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901130
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901131
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901141
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901138
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901139
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901147

Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901144
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901143
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901146
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901140
Airborne in-situ measurement of particle number concentration and size distribution using an optical particle counter during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301	Eppers, Oliver; Schneider, Johannes	2019-05-07	901137
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901196
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901202
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901194
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901201
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901200
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during ACLOUD 2017	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901209
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901193
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901205
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252201	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901206
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901207

Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901208
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901203
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270601	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901190
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901199
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705290701	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901191
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901197
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901195
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901198
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901192
Airborne in-situ measurement of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor and ozone during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001	Eppers, Oliver; Bozem, Heiko; Hoor, Peter	2019-05-08	901204
Liquid water path of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2018)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-27	902099
Liquid water path of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2016)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-27	902096
Liquid water path of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2017)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-27	902098
Integrated water vapor of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2018)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902143
Spectral solar cloud top radiance measured by airborne spectral imaging (AISA Hawk) during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Jäkel, Evelyn; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-05-28	902149
Integrated water vapor of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2016)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902140
Spectral solar cloud top radiance measured by airborne spectral imaging during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Jäkel, Evelyn; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-05-28	902150
Spectral solar cloud top radiance measured by airborne spectral imaging (AISA Eagle) during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Ehrlich, André; Schäfer, Michael; Jäkel, Evelyn; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-05-28	902148

Integrated water vapor of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2017)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902142
Temperature profile of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2017)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902146
Temperature profile of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2016)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902145
Temperature profile of HATPRO microwave radiometer at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2018)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-28	902147
HATPRO microwave radiometer measurements at AWIPEV, Ny-Ålesund (2016-2018)	Nomokonova, Tatiana; Ritter, Christoph; Ebell, Kerstin	2019-05-29	902183
PHIPS particle-by-particle data for the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Schnaiter, Martin; Järvinen, Emma	2019-06-13	902611
Collection of data sources for the Arctic CLOUD Observations Using airborne measurements during polar Day (ACLOUD) campaign, North-West of Svalbard between 23 May - 26 June 2017	Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Lüpkes, Christof; Buschmann, Matthias; Bozem, Heiko; Chechin, Dmitry; Clemen, Hans-Christian; Dupuy, Regis; Eppers, Oliver; Hartmann, Jörg; Herber, Andreas; Jäkel, Evelyn; Järvinen, Emma; Jourdan, Olivier; Kästner, Udo; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Köllner, Franziska; Mech, Mario; Mertes, Stephan; Neuber, Roland; Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Schnaiter, Martin; Schneider, Johannes; Stapf, Johannes; Zanatta, Marco	2019-06-13	902603
AMSR-2 winter snow depth on Arctic sea ice, Version 1.0 (NetCDF) (2012 to 2018)	Rostosky, Philip; Melsheimer, Christian; Spreen, Gunnar	2019-06-18	902747
AMSR-E winter snow depth on Arctic sea ice, Version 1.0 (NetCDF) (2002 to 2011)	Rostosky, Philip; Melsheimer, Christian; Spreen, Gunnar	2019-06-18	902748
1Hz resolution aircraft measurements of wind and temperature during the ACLOUD campaign in 2017	Hartmann, Jörg; Lüpkes, Christof; Chechin, Dmitry	2019-06-21	902849
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 5 campaign AFLUX 2019	Lüpkes, Christof; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Crewell, Susanne; Mech, Mario	2019-06-24	902876
ECHAM-HAM simulations for evaluation and quantification of BC effects in the Arctic under different emission data sets	Schacht, Jacob; Heinold, Bernd; Tegen, Ina	2019-07-05	903547
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-07-09	903690
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-07-09	903692
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-07-09	903691
LES of Arctic mixed-phase Stratocumulus (ACLOUD RF13)	Rauterkus, Robert; Ansorge, Cedrick	2019-08-02	904399
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170607_0845_1109)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905025
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170609_0827_0955)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905030
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170605_1715_1815)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905022

Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170609_0832_1003)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905016
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170610_1409_1813)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905018
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170605_1225_1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	904996
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170608_1258_1355)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905015
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170611_1255_1413)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905031
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170608_0904_1250)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905027
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170614_0833_1448)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905038
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170608_0922_1225)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905013
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170606_0852_1258)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905023
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170612_0924_1215)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905020
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170614_0829_1135)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905021
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170611_1421_1636)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905019
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2_20170611_1413_1625)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905036
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170607_1306_1524)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905002
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1_20170606_0851_1257)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	904999

Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2.20170608_1401_1546)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905029
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2.20170608_1303_1343)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905028
Broadband radiation measurements (package 2) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu2.20170612_0926_1217)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905037
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1.20170605_1706_1835)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	904997
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1.20170610_1016_1141)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905017
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign PASCAL in June 2017 (Balloon_Balu1.20170607_0843_1105)	Egerer, Ulrike; Gottschalk, Matthias; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred; Ehrlich, André	2019-08-16	905001
Phytoplankton pigment concentrations measured by HPLC during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.1	Liu, Yangyang; Hellmann, Sebastian; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-09-04	905502
Monthly geometric annual cycle of BrO vertical column densities per instrument	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp	2019-09-18	906043
Monthly tropospheric annual cycle of BrO vertical column densities per instrument	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp	2019-09-18	906045
Daily geometric annual cycle of BrO vertical column densities per instrument	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp	2019-09-18	906040
Climatologies of Geometric and Tropospheric BrO Vertical Column Densities derived from multiple UV-Vis Satellite Remote Sensors for Polar Spring over the Arctic	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp	2019-09-18	906046
Daily tropospheric annual cycle of BrO vertical column densities per instrument	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp	2019-09-18	906041
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705300801 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906627
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706131501 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906640
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091401 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906639
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081301 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906637

Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232101 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906652
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171801 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906646
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706041101 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906633
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during the aircraft ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906658
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706141601 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906642
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161701 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906644
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706181901 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906648
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202001 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906650
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262402 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906656
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262301 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906654
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021001 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906631
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051201 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906635
Liquid water content measured by the Nevzorov probe during flight P6.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705310901 of the ACLOUD campaign in the Arctic	Chechin, Dmitry	2019-09-26	906630
Tropospheric BrO vertical column densities	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp; Bajnai, David	2019-09-30	906972
Geometric BrO vertical column densities	Bougoudis, Ilias; Blechschmidt, Anne-Marlene; Richter, Andreas; Seo, Sora; Burrows, John Philipp; Bajnai, David	2019-09-30	906971
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705250701	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907099

Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706262401	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907096
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705311101	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907084
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706232201	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907093
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706252301	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907094
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706171901	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907090
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706051301	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907083
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705270801	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907082
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706202101	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907092
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706091501	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907088
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706081401	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907087
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706161801	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907089
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706021201	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907086
Aircraft measurements of AOD in the Arctic during the ACLOUD campaign 2017	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907097
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1705230601	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907080
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.206_ACLOUD.2017.1706182001	Herber, Andreas	2019-10-02	907091
TCCON data from Ny Ålesund, Spitsbergen (NO), Release GGG2014.R1	Notholt, Justus; Warneke, Thorsten; Petri, Christof; Deutscher, Nicholas M.; Weinzierl, Christine; Palm, Mathias; Buschmann, Matthias	2019-10-04	link
Spectrophotometric measurements of absorption coefficients and optical density by total particles, phytoplankton and non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907419
Standard deviation of optical density by non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907415
Standard deviation of absorption coefficient spectra of all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907413
Standard deviation of optical density by all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907418

Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907408
Optical density (median) by non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907414
Standard deviation of absorption coefficient spectra of non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907409
Optical density (median) by all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907416
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of phytoplankton during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907411
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS107	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-10	907412
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Wiegmann, Sonja; Liu, Yangyang; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-17	907603
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Wiegmann, Sonja; Liu, Yangyang; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-17	907604
Spectrophotometric measurements of absorption coefficients by total particles, phytoplankton and non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Wiegmann, Sonja; Liu, Yangyang; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-17	907605
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of phytoplankton during POLARSTERN cruise PS93.2	Wiegmann, Sonja; Liu, Yangyang; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-17	907593
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907646
Spectrophotometric measurements of absorption coefficients and optical density by total particles, phytoplankton and non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907648
Optical density (median) by all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907649
Standard deviation of optical density by all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907654
Standard deviation of optical density by non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907655
Standard deviation of absorption coefficient spectra of non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907653
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907640
Absorption coefficient spectra (median) of phytoplankton during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907647
Standard deviation of absorption coefficient spectra of all particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907651
Optical density (median) by non-algal particles during POLARSTERN cruise PS99	Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Bracher, Astrid	2019-10-18	907650
Cloud variables from ICON-LEM around Ny-Aalesund	Schemann, Vera	2019-10-30	link
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-11-05	908071
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-11-05	908072

High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2019-11-05	908070
Cloud radiative forcing, LWP and cloud-free albedo derived from airborne broadband irradiance observations during the ACLOUD campaign	Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Wendisch, Manfred	2019-12-02	909289
Free neutral monosaccharides and combined monosaccharides in seawater and related saline matrices	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Herrmann, Hartmut	2020-01-09	910575
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-01-21	911039
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-01-21	911040
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2019-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-01-21	911037
Updated microphysical cloud parameters retrieved from EM-FTIR spectra, measured during PS106 and PS107	Richter, Philipp; Palm, Mathias; Weinzierl, Christine; Notholt, Justus	2020-05-20	900377
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-05-26	917966
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-05-26	917950
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-05-26	917882
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2020-05-26	917967
Shipborne Ice Nucleating Particle (INP) measurements in the Arctic during PS106.1 and PS106.2	Hartmann, Markus; Gong, Xianda; Welti, André; Stratmann, Frank	2020-06-19	919194
Cloudnet target categorization during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-23	919344
OCEANET-ATMOSPHERE Microwave Radiometer HATPRO during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-24	919359
Cloudnet ice particles effective radius during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-25	919386
Cloudnet LWC during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-25	919383
Cloudnet liquid droplet effective radius during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-25	919399
Cloudnet IWC during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-26	919452
Cloudnet target classification during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-26	919463
OCEANET-ATMOSPHERE Cloud radar Mira-35 during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-06-29	919556
AMSR-E ASI sea ice concentration data, Arctic, version 5.4 (NetCDF) (June 2002 - September 2011)	Melsheimer, Christian; Spreen, Gunnar	2020-07-03	919777
LES results to accompany measurements at the POLARSTERN Research Vessel during the PASCAL field campaign on 7 June 2017	Neggens, Roel	2020-07-08	919946

LES results to accompany measurements at the POLARSTERN Research Vessel during the PASCAL field campaign on 6 June 2017	Neggers, Roel	2020-07-08	919945
OCEANET-ATMOSPHERE low level stratus clouds during PS106	Griesche, Hannes; Seifert, Patric; Engelman, Ronny; Radenz, Martin; Bühl, Johannes	2020-07-16	920246
Meteorological measurements by dropsondes released from POLAR 5 during AFLUX 2019	Becker, Sebastian; Ehrlich, André; Stapf, Johannes; Lüpkes, Christof; Mech, Mario; Crewell, Susanne; Wendisch, Manfred	2020-08-26	921996
Radiative energy budget, cloud radiative forcing, LWP, and cloud-free albedo derived from airborne broadband irradiance observations during AFLUX flight on 11 April 2019 (subset)	Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2020-09-02	922184
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 5 campaign P5.223.MOSAIC.ACA.2020	Herber, Andreas; Ehrlich, André; Lüpkes, Christof; Wendisch, Manfred; Mech, Mario	2020-11-10	924603
NDACC Measurements at the Ny-Ålesund Station	Palm, Mathias	2020-12-20	link
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926803
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926800
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-10)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926805
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926801
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926809
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926804
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-20	926802
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2020-11)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-01-21	926821
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180826_1424_1544)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927074
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180821_1115_1140)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927067
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180821_1027_1106)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927066
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180828_0934_1044)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927145
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180827_1442_1547)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927076
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180823_1302_1352)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927070
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180819_1433_1529)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927065
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180824_1619_1721)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927073

Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180818_1109_1138)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927114
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180823_1550_1629)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927071
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180910_1917_2002)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927096
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence and radiation during the Arctic field campaign Arctic Ocean 2018 in August/September 2018	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927100
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180823_1204_1253)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927122
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180821_1028_1106)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927119
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180910_0808_0938)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927095
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180824_1508_1602)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927072
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180827_1053_1115)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927075
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180909_0949_1102)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927091
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180820_1641_1709)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927117
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180826_1551_1643)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927144
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180823_1128_1200)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927121
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180911_0730_0851)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927097
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180823_1205_1253)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927069
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180824_1509_1602)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927123
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180910_0711_0800)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927094
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180818_1429_1524)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927064
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180909_0831_0941)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927090
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180828_1308_1434)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927146

Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180818.1109.1139)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927062
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180828.0934.1044)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927077
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180913.1321.1653)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927099
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180911.0858.1018)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927098
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180818.1429.1524)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927115
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180823.1128.1200)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927068
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180819.1433.1529)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927116
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180909.2028.2153)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927092
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 (Balloon_20180909.2201.2301)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-27	927093
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180824.1619.1721)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927174
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180911.0730.0851)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927164
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180910.2010.2129)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927157
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180820.1641.1709)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927171
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180827.1053.1115)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927178
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180823.1302.1352)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927173
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180826.1424.1543)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927175
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180909.2201.2301)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927153
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1_20180910.1917.2001)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927156

Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1.20180906_0733_1323)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927150
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1.20180909_0831_0941)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927152
Broadband radiation measurements (package 1) during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Balu1.20180910_0711_0800)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-28	927154
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h05_46203-46308 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927245
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h11_51185-51320 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927215
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h11_48390-48710 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927229
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h05_49838-49966 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927209
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h09_47570-47870 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927227
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h10_48040-48300 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927228
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h07_50285-50410 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927211
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h14_48352-48490 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927254
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h02_45505-45594 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927237
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h08_47210-47450 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927226
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h01_45298-45382 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927236
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h05_46035-46334 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927223
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h04_49628-49745 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927208
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h17_49295-49425 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927258
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h04_45623-45890 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927222
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180909_0950_1102)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-29	927203
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h09_46944-47090 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927248
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h04_45966-46088 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927239
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h02_49098-49217 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927206
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h13_49136-49430 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927231
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h07_46725-46833 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927247

Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h13.48125-48235 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927253
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h07.46864-47035 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927225
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180828.1308.1434)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-01-29	927202
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h10.50985-51117 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927214
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h01.48886-48980 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927205
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h12.47826-47950 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927252
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h14.49610-49845 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927232
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h03.49385-49510 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927207
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h06.50070-50184 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927210
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h02.44842-45108 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927220
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h06.46475-46710 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927224
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h12.48824-49060 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927230
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130310_SP50310h09.50740-50815 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927213
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h11.47559-47676 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927251
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h06.46457-46568 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927246

Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130326_SP50326h16_48967-49120 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927257
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during lead-parallel flight 20130325_SP50325h16_50405-50630 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-01-29	927234
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180910_0808_0938)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-01	927293
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during cross-lead flight zz1_20130310_cross-lead_SP50310h17_54271-55000_p5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-01	927298
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180910_2010_2129)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-01	927295
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during cross-lead flight zz1_20130325_cross-lead_SP50325h01_43682-44220_p5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-01	927299
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180909_2028_2153)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-01	927288
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during cross-lead flight zz1_20130326_cross-lead_SP50326h01_44143-44668_p5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-01	927300
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t16_51183-51206	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927359
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t20_51262-51282	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927363
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t17_51206-51222	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927360
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t06_50970-50990	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927349
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t18_51223-51247	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927361
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t13_51123-51140	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927356
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t14_51141-51165	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927357

Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t15_51167-51183	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927358
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t08_51010-51035	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927351
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t10_51053-51082	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927353
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during upwind flight 20130310_upwind_SP50310t01_47031-47190	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927368
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t05_50950-50970	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927348
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t19_51248-51261	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927362
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t12_51099-51123	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927355
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during upwind flight zz1_20130325_upwind_SP50325t01_44220-44425	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927369
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during upwind flight 20130326_upwind_SP50326t01_44668-44900	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927370
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t07_50990-51010	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927350
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t09_51035-51052	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927352
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t21_51283-51299	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927364
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t22_51300-51321	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927365
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t11_51082-51099	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927354
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during saw-tooth-lead flight 20130325_saw-tooth-lead_SP50325t04_51321-51528	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-02	927347

Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180911_0858_1018)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-02	927333
Mean quantities of wind, temperature, humidity, heat flux and momentum fluxes averaged over the lead-parallel flight legs of flight STABLE_1303100106	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-03	927389
Mean quantities of wind, temperature, humidity, heat flux and momentum fluxes averaged over the lead-parallel flight legs of flight STABLE_1303250114	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-03	927390
Mean quantities of wind, temperature, humidity, heat flux and momentum fluxes averaged over the lead-parallel flight legs of flight STABLE_1303260115	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-02-03	927391
Dissolved and particulate carbohydrates and inorganic ions in Antarctic surface seawater samples	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; Fuchs, Susanne; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Sotomayor Garcia, Ana; Cabrera Brufau, Miguel; Vaqué, Dolors; Berdalet, Elisa; Dall'Osto, Manuel; Herrmann, Hartmut	2021-02-05	927566
Marine carbohydrates and inorganic ions in size-resolved atmospheric particles collected over the Southern Ocean	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; Fuchs, Susanne; Rödger, Susanne; Dietze, Anett; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Herrmann, Hartmut	2021-02-05	927565
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_Hotwire_20180828_1054_1305)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-05	927550
Tethered balloon-borne turbulence measurements during the Arctic field campaign AO2018 in 2018 (Balloon_20180906_0733_1323)	Gottschalk, Matthias; Egerer, Ulrike	2021-02-05	927547
The Importance of the Representation of DMS Oxidation in Global Chemistry-Climate Simulations	Hoffmann, Erik Hans; Heinold, Bernd; Kubin, Anne; Tegen, Ina; Herrmann, Hartmut	2021-03-30	link
Spectral solar cloud top and surface radiance measured by airborne spectral imaging during the AFLUX campaign in 2019	Schäfer, Michael; Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-04-30	930932
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-13 from 11:53 to 15:20 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-10	931300
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-10 from 12:06 to 12:48 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-10	931299
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-21 from 11:35 to 13:04 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931391
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-14 from 13:20 to 14:48 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931387
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-26 from 11:58 to 13:36 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931394
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-23 from 11:08 to 12:36 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931392
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-15 from 11:45 to 14:43 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931388

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-07-24 from 10:17 to 11:53 during MOSAiC leg 4	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-11	931393
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence during MOSAiC leg 4 in July 2020	Egerer, Ulrike; Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-05-12	931404
Mean spectral diffuse attenuation coefficients from 318 to 952 nm of underwater light profiles measured at discrete stations with radiometry during RV Polarstern cruise PS113 in the Atlantic Ocean	Bracher, Astrid; Dinter, Tilman	2021-05-14	931480
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-05-19	931686
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-05-19	931688
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-02)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-05-19	931685
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-01)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-05-19	931681
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence during the MOSAiC expedition from December 2019 to May 2020	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-06-01	932007
Aircraft measurements of broadband irradiance during the AFLUX campaign in 2019	Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-06-02	932020
Cloud radiative forcing, LWP and cloud-free albedo derived from airborne broadband irradiance observations during the AFLUX and ALOUD campaign	Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-06-02	932010
Collection of data sets for the MOSAiC Airborne observations in the Central Arctic (MOSAiC-ACA) campaign, carried out in late summer 2020 northwest of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Lüpkes, Christof; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Crewell, Susanne; Becker, Sebastian; Chechin, Dmitry; Dupuy, Regis; Goubeyre, Christophe; Hahn, Valerian; Jäkel, Evelyn; Jansen, Friedhelm; Jourdan, Olivier; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Klingebiel, Marcus; Krobot, Pavel; Kulla, Birte Solveig; Risse, Nils; Mioche, Guillaume; Moser, Manuel; Schäfer, Michael; Voigt, Christiane	2021-06-08	932295
Collection of data sets for the Airborne measurements of radiative and turbulent FLUXes of energy and momentum in the Arctic boundary layer (AFLUX) campaign, carried out in spring 2019 northwest of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Lüpkes, Christof; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred; Crewell, Susanne; Becker, Sebastian; Boose, Yvonne; Chechin, Dmitry; Dupuy, Regis; Goubeyre, Christophe; Jäkel, Evelyn; Jourdan, Olivier; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Klingebiel, Marcus; Krobot, Pavel; Kulla, Birte Solveig; Risse, Nils; Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Mioche, Guillaume; Moser, Manuel; Schäfer, Michael; Stapf, Johannes; Voigt, Christiane	2021-06-08	932294
Cloud top altitude retrieved from Lidar measurements during ALOUD at 1 second resolution	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Ritter, Christoph	2021-06-09	932454
Cloud top altitude retrieved from Lidar measurements during MOSAiC-ACA at 1 second resolution	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Ritter, Christoph	2021-06-10	932456
Cloud top altitude retrieved from Lidar measurements during AFLUX at 1 second resolution	Kulla, Birte Solveig; Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Ritter, Christoph	2021-06-10	932455

Optical-equivalent snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral surface albedo measurements during PAMARCMiP 2018, flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803260501	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Herber, Andreas; Carlsen, Tim	2021-06-11	932523
Optical-equivalent snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral surface albedo measurements during PAMARCMiP 2018	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Herber, Andreas; Carlsen, Tim	2021-06-11	932527
Optical-equivalent snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral surface albedo measurements during PAMARCMiP 2018, flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803270701	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Herber, Andreas; Carlsen, Tim	2021-06-11	932526
Optical-equivalent snow grain size retrieved from airborne spectral surface albedo measurements during PAMARCMiP 2018, flight P5.210_PAMARCMIP_2018_1803250401	Jäkel, Evelyn; Ehrlich, André; Herber, Andreas; Carlsen, Tim	2021-06-11	932522
Inorganic ions in fog water sampled from the Arctic in 2017	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Fuchs, Susanne; Hartmann, Markus; Gong, Xianda; Herrmann, Hartmut	2021-06-14	932573
Inorganic ions in size-resolved aerosol particles sampled from the Arctic in 2017	Zeppenfeld, Sebastian; van Pinxteren, Manuela; Fuchs, Susanne; Hartmann, Markus; Gong, Xianda; Herrmann, Hartmut	2021-06-14	932569
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180325_1313_1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933206
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180326_1108_1236)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933224
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180330_0806_0958)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933217
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180324_1346_1453)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933204
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180322_1542_1652)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933202
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1336_1718)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933213
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180330_0258_0726)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933216
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180326_1310_1709)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933209
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180328_1123_1508)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933211
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180404_1025_1502)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933227
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180327_1106_1556)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933210
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1752_2216)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933214

Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180403_1657_2044)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933221
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180322_1156_1353)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933201
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933223
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180402_1005_1232)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933220
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180324_1530_1611)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933205
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_1202_1301)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933212
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180323_1217_1533)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933203
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180401_1034_1151)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933226
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180329_2240_0014)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933215
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180401_1248_1544)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933219
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180321_1737_1937)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933200
Tethered balloon-borne meteorological measurements during the Arctic field campaign PAMARCMiP (Balloon_20180325_1537_1614)	Egerer, Ulrike; Siebert, Holger; Voigtländer, Jens; Gottschalk, Matthias	2021-06-30	933207
Liquid Water Path over sea ice free Arctic ocean derived from passive microwave airborne measurements during ACLOUD in May/June 2017	Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Mech, Mario	2021-07-06	933387
Meteorological measurements by dropsondes released from POLAR 5 during MOSAiC-ACA 2020	Becker, Sebastian; Ehrlich, André; Mech, Mario; Lüpkes, Christof; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-07-12	933581
Radiance fields of clouds and the Arctic surface measured by a digital camera during AFLUX	Jäkel, Evelyn; Stapf, Johannes; Schäfer, Michael; Ruiz-Donoso, Elena; Ehrlich, André; Rosenburg, Sophie	2021-07-20	933839
Radiance fields of clouds and the Arctic surface measured by a digital camera during MOSAiC-ACA	Jäkel, Evelyn; Schäfer, Michael; Ehrlich, André; Becker, Sebastian; Klingebiel, Marcus; Rosenburg, Sophie	2021-07-20	933849
Microphysical Cloud Parameters and water paths retrieved from EM-FIR spectra, measured during PS106 and PS107 in Arctic summer 2017	Richter, Philipp; Palm, Mathias; Weinzierl, Christine; Notholt, Justus	2021-07-20	933829
Aircraft measurements of spectral solar up- and downward irradiances in the Arctic during the MOSAiC-ACA campaign 2020	Jäkel, Evelyn; Schäfer, Michael; Ehrlich, André; Becker, Sebastian; Klingebiel, Marcus	2021-07-20	933850
Pan-Arctic spectral reflectances at the top-of-atmosphere between 1996 and 2018	Lelli, Luca; Vountas, Marco; Khosravi, Narges; Burrows, John Philipp	2021-07-22	933905
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-02-06 from 11:19 to 11:31 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934501

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-06 from 11:22 to 11:40 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934487
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-29 from 08:06 to 08:16 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934477
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-02-15 from 11:05 to 11:20 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934505
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-06 from 18:58 to 19:18 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934465
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-22 from 13:19 to 13:40 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934495
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-22 from 14:17 to 14:23 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934513
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-07 from 06:05 to 06:12 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934466
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-06 from 12:18 to 12:37 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934463
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-12 from 07:48 to 08:15 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934470
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-25 from 07:26 to 07:43 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934497
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-05 from 12:29 to 12:47 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934507
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-22 from 13:29 to 13:46 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934510
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-22 from 14:10 to 14:16 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934512
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-29 from 11:56 to 12:09 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934479
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-23 from 12:17 to 12:40 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934515
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-25 from 12:25 to 12:39 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934500
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-22 from 08:54 to 08:59 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934508
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-24 from 11:45 to 12:10 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934517
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-24 from 13:13 to 13:31 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934519
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-08 from 07:34 to 08:03 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934491

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-11 from 12:57 to 13:11 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934468
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-24 from 08:49 to 09:22 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934516
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-23 from 11:30 to 11:43 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934472
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-25 from 12:07 to 12:23 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934499
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-29 from 07:50 to 08:02 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934476
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-05 from 12:10 to 12:25 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934506
An overview of tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence during the MOSAiC expedition from December 2019 to May 2020	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934458
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-23 from 11:42 to 12:10 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934514
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-29 from 11:27 to 11:44 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934478
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-07 from 07:19 to 07:37 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934488
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-02-15 from 10:15 to 10:25 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934503
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-25 from 11:08 to 11:25 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934498
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-06 from 18:15 to 18:43 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934464
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-05 from 13:17 to 13:30 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934485
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-23 from 11:10 to 11:23 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934471
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-05 from 11:51 to 12:06 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934480
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-02-15 from 10:44 to 11:00 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934504
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-24 from 12:47 to 13:07 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934518
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-28 from 11:35 to 11:46 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934474
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-23 from 12:54 to 13:08 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934473

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-05 from 13:01 to 13:13 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934482
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-02-06 from 11:36 to 11:55 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934502
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-22 from 13:01 to 13:17 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934493
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-28 from 13:18 to 13:32 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934475
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-07 from 06:13 to 06:24 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934467
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-05 from 12:19 to 12:29 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934481
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-06 from 10:57 to 11:15 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934486
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2019-12-11 from 13:28 to 13:44 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934469
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-01-07 from 07:44 to 08:04 during MOSAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934490
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-22 from 13:53 to 14:10 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-04	934511
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-05 from 11:40 to 11:55 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934567
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-24 from 14:21 to 14:47 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934543
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-07 from 09:01 to 09:07 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934531
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-24 from 15:01 to 15:10 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934545
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-17 from 11:55 to 12:07 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934538
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-06 from 12:21 to 12:42 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934528
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-04 from 08:40 to 09:14 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934558
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-24 from 13:39 to 14:07 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934542
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-25 from 14:42 to 14:51 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934547
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-07 from 11:46 to 12:26 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934532

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-07 from 14:10 to 14:37 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934533
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-26 from 12:20 to 12:47 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934548
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-27 from 08:52 to 09:06 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934555
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-10 from 11:33 to 11:58 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934534
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-26 from 14:57 to 15:05 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934552
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-10 from 14:26 to 14:48 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934535
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-24 from 08:32 to 09:04 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934541
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-07 from 08:35 to 08:40 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934530
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-04 from 12:36 to 13:05 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934561
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-24 from 14:47 to 14:59 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934544
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-30 from 13:28 to 13:56 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934526
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-06 from 08:08 to 08:18 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934569
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-05 from 12:12 to 12:25 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934568
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-04 from 13:10 to 13:41 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934565
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-03-30 from 13:57 to 14:24 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934527
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-06 from 12:47 to 13:07 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934529
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-23 from 14:31 to 15:02 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934540
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-05 from 08:46 to 09:04 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934566
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-26 from 14:44 to 14:55 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934550
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-23 from 12:31 to 13:01 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934539

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-30 from 12:19 to 12:43 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934556
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-06 from 12:12 to 12:29 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934571
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-06 from 11:42 to 12:09 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934570
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-25 from 12:58 to 13:08 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934546
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-26 from 14:20 to 14:39 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934549
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-01 from 12:06 to 12:25 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934557
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-04-27 from 08:30 to 08:50 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934553
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of turbulence on 2020-05-04 from 11:40 to 12:04 during MOSAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2021-08-05	934559
Aircraft measurements of broadband irradiance during the MOSAiC-ACA campaign in 2020	Becker, Sebastian; Stapf, Johannes; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2021-09-24	936232
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130304-D4.155317	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936615
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D8.151804	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936632
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D2.141332	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936626
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130307-D1.150642	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936622
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130306_T3 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936660
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D7.151024	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936631
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130304-D1.151939	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936612
Airborne and dropsonde measurements in MCAOs during STABLE in March 2013	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936635
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130307-D3.154647	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936624
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D5.145217	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936629

Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130304.T3 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936646
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130307-D2.151752	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936623
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130306-D2.152803	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936618
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130304-D2.153119	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936613
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130306.T4 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936661
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130304-D5.160455	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936616
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130306.T6 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936664
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130306-D3.153803	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936619
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130306-D5.160645	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936621
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130304.T1 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936639
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D1.115403	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936625
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130306.T5 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936663
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130304.T2 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936645
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130306-D1.151627	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936617
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130306.T1 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936655
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130304.T4 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936647
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130304.T6 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936650
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130306-D4.154905	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936620
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130307.T1 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936666
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D4.144221	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936628
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130304-D3.154208	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936614
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130306_T7 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936665
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Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity by dropsonde 20130326-D9.152729	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936633
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the descending profile 20130306_T2 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936656
Measurements of wind, temperature, pressure and humidity during the ascending profile 20130304_T5 with POLAR 5	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Schmitt, Amelie U; Birnbaum, Gerit; Vihma, Timo; Michaelis, Janosch	2021-10-04	936648
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High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-10-12	937217
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-10-12	937219
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-08)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-10-12	937222
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-09)	Maturilli, Marion	2021-10-12	937224
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Spectrophotometric measurements of absorption coefficients by phytoplankton during HEINCKE cruise HE462 in the North Sea and Sogne Fjord from 29 April to 7 May 2016	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja	2021-11-12	938153
Spectrophotometric measurements of absorption coefficients by non-algal particles in the Atlantic Southern Ocean during RV POLARSTERN cruise PS103 in Dec 2016 to Jan 2017	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang	2021-11-15	938196
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Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter obtained underway with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during HEINCKE cruise HE462 in the North Sea and Sogne Fjord	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-18	938384
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter obtained at fixed stations with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during HEINCKE cruise HE462 in the North Sea and Sogne Fjord	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-18	938383
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter across the Atlantic Ocean measured at fixed stations with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS113	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Xi, Hongyan; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-18	938399
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter across the Atlantic Ocean measured underway with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS113	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Xi, Hongyan; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-18	938400
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) from North Sea to Fram Strait measured underway with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS121	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-19	938473
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) from North Sea to Fram Strait measured at fixed stations with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS121	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Wiegmann, Sonja; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-19	938472
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter across the South Atlantic Ocean measured at fixed stations with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS103	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Oelker, Julia; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-19	938467
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter across the South Atlantic Ocean measured underway with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS103	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Oelker, Julia; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-19	938468
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter from North Sea to Fram Strait measured underway with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.1	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Hellmann, Sebastian; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-22	938494
Absorption coefficients by coloured dissolved organic matter from North Sea to Fram Strait measured at fixed stations with a Liquid Waveguide Capillary Cell system during POLARSTERN cruise PS99.1	Bracher, Astrid; Liu, Yangyang; Hellmann, Sebastian; Bensi, Manuel; Kovacevic, Vedrana; Röttgers, Rüdiger	2021-11-22	938491
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Physical Oceanography measured with UCTD (Underway CTD) during MERIAN cruise MSM93	Hofmann, Zerlina; von Appen, Wilken-Jon; Mathieu, Laura; Hagemann, Jonas; Engicht, Carina; Kuhlmeiy, David	2021-12-20	939712
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Physical Oceanography measured with CTD on Triaxus topAWI (towed ocean profiler of the AWI) during MERIAN cruise MSM93	Hofmann, Zerlina; von Appen, Wilken-Jon; Mathieu, Laura; Hagemann, Jonas; Engicht, Carina; Kuhlmeiy, David; Becker, Hauke	2022-01-13	940010
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Mean spectral diffuse attenuation coefficients averaged for 320 nm to 338.5 nm (UVAB), 356.5 nm to 390 nm (UVA) and 390 nm to 423 nm (blue) in the Atlantic Ocean from Sentinel-5P instrument TROPOMI	Oelker, Julia; Richter, Andreas; Losa, Svetlana N; Alvarado, Leonardo M A; Bracher, Astrid	2022-01-26	940352
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Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature maps with 5 m resolution during the MOSAiC expedition, NetCDF format, version 2	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-02-09	940841
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature images during the MOSAiC expedition, NetCDF format, version 2	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-02-09	940847
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature maps with 1 m resolution during the MOSAiC expedition, NetCDF format, version 2	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-02-09	940846
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature maps during the MOSAiC expedition, png format, version 2	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-02-09	940840
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperatures during the MOSAiC expedition, version 2	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-02-11	941017
Phytoplankton pigment concentrations during POLARSTERN cruise PS121 from North Sea to Fram in August to September 2019	Bracher, Astrid; Wiegmann, Sonja	2022-02-11	941011

Brightness temperatures of the HATPRO microwave radiometer onboard the Polarstern during the MOSAiC expedition	Engelmann, Ronny; Griesche, Hannes; Radenz, Martin; Hofer, Julian; Althausen, Dietrich; Walbröl, Andreas; Ebell, Kerstin	2022-02-22	941356
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Temperature and humidity profiles, integrated water vapour and liquid water path derived from the HATPRO microwave radiometer onboard the Polarstern during the MOSAiC expedition	Ebell, Kerstin; Walbröl, Andreas; Engelmann, Ronny; Griesche, Hannes; Radenz, Martin; Hofer, Julian; Althausen, Dietrich	2022-02-23	941389
Integrated water vapour derived from the MiRAC-P microwave radiometer onboard the Polarstern during the MOSAiC expedition	Walbröl, Andreas; Orlandi, Emiliano; Crewell, Susanne; Ebell, Kerstin	2022-02-24	941470
French Airborne Measurement Platform (PMA) cloud particle size distribution and volumic cloud particle diffusion properties dataset near Svalbard for AFLUX measurement campaign with POLAR 5 in 2019	Dupuy, Regis; Gourbeyre, Christophe; Mioche, Guillaume; Jourdan, Olivier	2022-02-25	941498
French Airborne Measurement Platform (PMA) cloud particle size distribution and volumic cloud particle diffusion properties dataset near Svalbard for MOSAIC-ACA measurement campaign in 2020	Dupuy, Regis; Gourbeyre, Christophe; Mioche, Guillaume; Moser, Manuel; Jourdan, Olivier	2022-02-28	941538
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High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2021-12)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-03-09	942085
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Physical properties of sea ice cores from site BGC1 measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Damm, Ellen; Simões Pereira, Patric; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Dumitrascu, Adela; Marsay, Christopher M; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-05	943768
Physical properties of sea ice cores from site BGC3 measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Damm, Ellen; Simões Pereira, Patric; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Dumitrascu, Adela; Marsay, Christopher M; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943813
Physical properties of sea ice cores from L sites measured on leg 1 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Damm, Ellen; Simões Pereira, Patric; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Dumitrascu, Adela; Marsay, Christopher M; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943815
Physical properties of sea ice cores from site MCS_FYI measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Castellani, Giulia; Creamean, Jessie; Damm, Ellen; Divine, Dmitry V; Dumitrascu, Adela; Eggers, Lena; Fong, Allison A; Fons, Steven W; Gradinger, Rolf; Granskog, Mats A; Grosse, Julia; Haapala, Jari; Haas, Christian; Hoppe, Clara Jule Marie; Høyland, Knut Vilhelm; Immerz, Antonia; Kolabutin, Nikolai; Krumpfen, Thomas; Lei, Ruibo; Marsay, Christopher M; Maus, Sönke; Nicolaus, Marcel; Nubom, Alexey; Oggier, Marc; Olsen, Lasse Mork; Rember, Robert; Ren, Jian; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Sheikin, Igor; Shimanchuk, Egor; Simões Pereira, Patric; Spahic, Susanne; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Torres-Valdés, Sinhué; Torstenson, Anders; Ulfsbo, Adam; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Wischnewski, Laura; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943817

Physical properties of sea ice cores for biogeochemistry studies measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Damm, Ellen; Simões Pereira, Patric; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Castellani, Giulia; Creamean, Jessie; Divine, Dmitry V; Dumitrascu, Adela; Eggers, Lena; Fong, Allison A; Fons, Steven W; Gradinger, Rolf; Granskog, Mats A; Grosse, Julia; Haapala, Jari; Haas, Christian; Hoppe, Clara Jule Marie; Høyland, Knut Vilhelm; Immerz, Antonia; Kolabutin, Nikolai; Krumpfen, Thomas; Lei, Ruibo; Marsay, Christopher M; Maus, Sönke; Nicolaus, Marcel; Nubom, Alexey; Oggier, Marc; Olsen, Lasse Mork; Rember, Robert; Ren, Jian; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Sheikin, Igor; Shimanchuk, Egor; Torres-Valdés, Sinhué; Spahic, Susanne; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Torstensson, Anders; Ulfbo, Adam; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Wischnewski, Laura; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943811
Physical properties of sea ice cores from site MCS-SYI measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Castellani, Giulia; Creamean, Jessie; Damm, Ellen; Divine, Dmitry V; Dumitrascu, Adela; Eggers, Lena; Fong, Allison A; Fons, Steven W; Gradinger, Rolf; Granskog, Mats A; Grosse, Julia; Haapala, Jari; Haas, Christian; Hoppe, Clara Jule Marie; Høyland, Knut Vilhelm; Immerz, Antonia; Kolabutin, Nikolai; Krumpfen, Thomas; Lei, Ruibo; Marsay, Christopher M; Maus, Sönke; Nicolaus, Marcel; Nubom, Alexey; Oggier, Marc; Olsen, Lasse Mork; Rember, Robert; Ren, Jian; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Sheikin, Igor; Shimanchuk, Egor; Simões Pereira, Patric; Spahic, Susanne; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Torres-Valdés, Sinhué; Torstensson, Anders; Ulfbo, Adam; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Wischnewski, Laura; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943818
Physical properties of sea ice cores from site BGC2 measured on legs 1 to 3 of the MOSAiC expedition	Angelopoulos, Michael; Damm, Ellen; Simões Pereira, Patric; Abrahamsson, Katarina; Bauch, Dorothea; Bowman, Jeff S; Dumitrascu, Adela; Marsay, Christopher M; Rinke, Annette; Sachs, Torsten; Stefels, Jacqueline; Stephens, Mark; Verdugo, Josefa; Wang, Lei; Zhan, Liyang	2022-05-06	943812
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-19, flight PS122/4.47-170	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943896
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-13, flight PS122/4.47-98	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943892
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-23, flight PS122/4.48-137	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943902

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-27, flight PS122/4_49-98	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943906
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-26, flight PS122/4_48-218	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943905
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-06-29, flight PS122/4_45-156	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943890
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-20, flight PS122/4_48-127	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943897
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-21, flight PS122/4_48-128	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943898
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-14, flight PS122/4_47-100	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943893
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-15, flight PS122/4_47-166	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943894
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-22, flight PS122/4_48-132	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943900
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-23, flight PS122/4_48-134	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943901
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics during the MO-SAiC expedition from June to July 2020	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943907
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-10, flight PS122/4_46-182	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943891
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-24, flight PS122/4_48-138	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943903
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-15, flight PS122/4_47-169	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943895
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-06-29, flight PS122/4_45-141	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943912
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-21, flight PS122/4_48-130	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943899
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of aerosol particle microphysics on 2020-07-25, flight PS122/4_48-216	Pilz, Christian; Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wehner, Birgit	2022-05-11	943904
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during flight 8 (PS122/4_47-165)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944066
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during flight 11 (PS122/4_47-168)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944063
Microwave brightness temperature measurements during the AFLUX Arctic airborne campaign in spring 2019 out of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Crewell, Susanne; Kulla, Birte Solveig; Krobot, Pavel	2022-05-12	944057
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during flight 10 (PS122/4_47-167)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944062

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during MOSAiC leg 4 in July 2020	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944068
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during flight 28 (PS122/4.48-140)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944064
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of liquid cloud water presence during flight 6 (PS122/4.47-99)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-12	944065
Microwave brightness temperature measurements during the ACLOUD Arctic airborne campaign in early summer 2017 out of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Crewell, Susanne; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard; Krobot, Pavel	2022-05-12	944070
Microwave brightness temperature measurements during the MOSAiC-ACA Arctic airborne campaign in late summer 2020 out of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Crewell, Susanne; Jansen, Friedhelm	2022-05-12	944101
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 11 (PS122/4.47-168)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944181
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 6 (PS122/4.47-99)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944196
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 14 (PS122/4.47-171)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944182
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 33 (PS122/4.49-98)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944193
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 32 (PS122/4.48-218)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944192
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 11 (PS122/4.47-168)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944212
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 4 (PS122/4.46-183)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944195
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 1 (PS122/4.45-141)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944209
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 30 (PS122/4.48-216)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944221
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 24 (PS122/4.48-135)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944218
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 10 (PS122/4.47-167)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944211
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 22 (PS122/4.48-133)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944217
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 33 (PS122/4.49-98)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944224
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 4 (PS122/4.46-183)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944226

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 2 (PS122/4.45-156)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944214
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 31 (PS122/4.48-217)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944191
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during MOSAiC leg 4 in July 2020	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944200
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 27 (PS122/4.48-139)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944189
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 24 (PS122/4.48-135)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944188
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 31 (PS122/4.48-217)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944222
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 14 (PS122/4.47-171)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944213
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 30 (PS122/4.48-216)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944190
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during MOSAiC leg 4 in July 2020	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944232
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 8 (PS122/4.47-165)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944230
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 34 (PS122/4.49-98)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944194
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 34 (PS122/4.49-98)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944225
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 6 (PS122/4.47-99)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944227
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 1 (PS122/4.45-141)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944179
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 27 (PS122/4.48-139)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944219
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 20 (PS122/4.48-131)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944216
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 32 (PS122/4.48-218)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944223
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 8 (PS122/4.47-165)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944197
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 10 (PS122/4.47-167)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944180
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 2 (PS122/4.45-156)	Lonardi, Michael; Siebert, Holger; Wendisch, Manfred	Pilz, Christian; Ehrlich, André;	2022-05-13	944184

Tethered balloon-borne measurements of solar radiation during flight 9 (PS122/4.47-166)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944231
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 22 (PS122/4.48-133)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944187
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 9 (PS122/4.47-166)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944198
Tethered balloon-borne measurements of terrestrial radiation during flight 20 (PS122/4.48-131)	Lonardi, Michael; Pilz, Christian; Siebert, Holger; Ehrlich, André; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-05-13	944185
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2022-04)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-05-20	944409
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2022-03)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-05-20	944406
Radar reflectivities at 94 GHz and microwave brightness temperature measurements at 89 GHz during the AFLUX Arctic airborne campaign in spring 2019 out of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Crewell, Susanne; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard	2022-05-23	944506
Radar reflectivities at 94 GHz and microwave brightness temperature measurements at 89 GHz during the MOSAiC-ACA Arctic airborne campaign	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Crewell, Susanne; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard	2022-05-23	944507
Ny-Aalesund ICON-LEM 600m meteograms from Aug. to Dec. 2020	Schemann, Vera	2022-06-15	link
High resolution aircraft measurements of wind and temperature during the AFLUX campaign in 2019	Lüpkes, Christof; Hartmann, Jörg; Chechin, Dmitry; Michaelis, Janosch	2022-07-04	945844
Radar reflectivities at 94 GHz and microwave brightness temperature measurements at 89 GHz during the ACLOUD Arctic airborne campaign in early summer 2017 out of Svalbard	Mech, Mario; Risse, Nils; Crewell, Susanne; Kliesch, Leif-Leonard	2022-07-05	945988
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2022-07)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-08-08	946901
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2022-06)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-08-08	946898
High resolution radiosonde measurements from station Ny-Ålesund (2022-05)	Maturilli, Marion	2022-08-08	946896
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903210301	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-09	946922
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during the AFLUX campaign 2019	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-09	946923
Spectral solar cloud top and surface radiance measured by airborne spectral imaging during the MOSAiC-ACA campaign in September 2020	Schäfer, Michael; Ehrlich, André; Jäkel, Evelyn; Klingebiel, Marcus; Becker, Sebastian; Wendisch, Manfred	2022-08-10	946965
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903230401	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947002
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1904031002	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947009
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903300701	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947005

Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903250602	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947004
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1904061202	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947010
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1904071301	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947012
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1904081401	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947014
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1904111501	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947016
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903240501	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947003
Aircraft measurements of aerosol optical depth in the Arctic during flight P5.216_AFLUX_2019_1903310801	Herber, Andreas	2022-08-11	947007
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180525_47	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947174
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180426_03	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947125
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180515_13	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947139
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180525_46	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947173
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180501_06	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947128
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180523_39	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947166
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180525_48	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947175
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180521_30	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947156
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180523_38	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947165
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180501_04	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947126

Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180525_50	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947177
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA in Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen, April/May 2018	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947132
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180521_35	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947162
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180515_12	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947138
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180521_32	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947159
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight 20180424.01	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947121
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180523_37	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947164
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180525_49	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947176
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180519_21	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947147
Arctic aerosol and atmospheric observations with the unmanned research aircraft ALADINA during flight ALADINA_20180519_23	Harm-Altstädter, Barbara; Bärfuss, Konrad; Bretschneider, Lutz; Käthner, Ralf; Pätzold, Falk; Peuker, Alexander; Wehner, Birgit; Lampert, Astrid	2022-08-17	947149
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 6 campaign P6_231_HALO_2022	Herber, Andreas; Schneider, Johannes; Borrmann, Stephan; Voigt, Christiane; Moser, Manuel	2022-08-30	947701
Master tracks in different resolutions during POLAR 5 campaign P5_232_HALO_2022	Herber, Andreas; Mech, Mario; Klingebiel, Marcus; Lüpkes, Christof	2022-08-31	947788
High resolution aircraft measurements of wind and temperature during the MOSAIC-ACA campaign in 2020	Hartmann, Jörg; Lüpkes, Christof; Michaelis, Janosch; Herber, Andreas	2022-08-31	947787
TCCON data from Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard (NO), Release GGG2020.R0	Buschmann, Matthias; Petri, Christof; Palm, Mathias; Warneke, Thorsten; Notholt, Justus	2022-09-20	link
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements during the MOSAiC expedition from December 2019 to May 2020	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-20	948546
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-06 from 12:18 to 12:37 during MOSAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-20	948545

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-27 from 08:52 to 09:06 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948799
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-11 from 12:57 to 13:11 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948729
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-24 from 12:47 to 13:07 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948772
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-22 from 08:54 to 08:59 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948763
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-07 from 11:46 to 12:26 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948780
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-24 from 08:32 to 09:04 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948787
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-08 from 07:34 to 08:03 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948749
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-23 from 11:30 to 11:43 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948733
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-04 from 13:10 to 13:41 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948806
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-05 from 12:12 to 12:25 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948809
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-23 from 12:54 to 13:08 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948734
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-05 from 13:17 to 13:30 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948744
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-07 from 06:13 to 06:24 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948728
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-02-15 from 10:44 to 11:00 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948759
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-06 from 12:21 to 12:42 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948776

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-30 from 12:19 to 12:43 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948800
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-06 from 12:12 to 12:29 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948812
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-24 from 08:49 to 09:22 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948770
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-22 from 13:01 to 13:17 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948750
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-24 from 14:21 to 14:47 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948789
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-07 from 07:19 to 07:37 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948747
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-25 from 14:42 to 14:51 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948793
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-05 from 11:40 to 11:55 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948808
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-01 from 12:06 to 12:25 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948801
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-27 from 08:30 to 08:50 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948798
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-11 from 13:28 to 13:44 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948730
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-30 from 13:28 to 13:56 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948774
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-25 from 12:07 to 12:23 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948754
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-05 from 13:01 to 13:13 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948743
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-26 from 14:20 to 14:39 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948795

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-07 from 06:05 to 06:12 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948727
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-06 from 11:42 to 12:09 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948811
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-23 from 14:31 to 15:02 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948786
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-28 from 13:18 to 13:32 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948736
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-26 from 14:44 to 14:55 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948796
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-06 from 08:08 to 08:18 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948810
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-04 from 12:36 to 13:05 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948805
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-22 from 13:53 to 14:10 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948765
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-26 from 14:57 to 15:05 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948797
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-29 from 11:27 to 11:44 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948739
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-06 from 11:22 to 11:40 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948746
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-24 from 14:47 to 14:59 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948790
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-25 from 07:26 to 07:43 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948752
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-05 from 12:29 to 12:47 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948762
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-25 from 11:08 to 11:25 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948753

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-07 from 14:10 to 14:37 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948781
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-02-06 from 11:36 to 11:55 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948757
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-06 from 12:47 to 13:07 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948777
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-24 from 13:13 to 13:31 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948773
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-24 from 13:39 to 14:07 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948788
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-02-06 from 11:19 to 11:31 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948756
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-07 from 09:01 to 09:07 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948779
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-25 from 12:58 to 13:08 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948792
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-22 from 13:29 to 13:46 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948764
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-22 from 14:17 to 14:23 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948767
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-12 from 07:48 to 08:15 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948731
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-04 from 08:40 to 09:14 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948803
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-29 from 07:50 to 08:02 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948737
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-29 from 11:56 to 12:09 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948740
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-05 from 11:51 to 12:06 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948741

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-28 from 11:35 to 11:46 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948735
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-05 from 12:19 to 12:29 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948742
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-23 from 12:17 to 12:40 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948769
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-07 from 07:44 to 08:04 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948748
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-23 from 11:42 to 12:10 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948768
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-06 from 18:15 to 18:43 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948720
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-29 from 08:06 to 08:16 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948738
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-06 from 10:57 to 11:15 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948745
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-22 from 14:10 to 14:16 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948766
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-30 from 13:57 to 14:24 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948775
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-17 from 11:55 to 12:07 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948784
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-25 from 12:25 to 12:39 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948755
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-10 from 11:33 to 11:58 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948782
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-01-22 from 13:19 to 13:40 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948751
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-24 from 15:01 to 15:10 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948791

Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-23 from 11:10 to 11:23 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948732
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-04 from 11:40 to 12:04 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948804
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-23 from 12:31 to 13:01 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948785
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-07 from 08:35 to 08:40 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948778
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-24 from 11:45 to 12:10 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948771
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-03-05 from 12:10 to 12:25 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948761
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-05-05 from 08:46 to 09:04 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948807
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-02-15 from 10:15 to 10:25 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948758
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-10 from 14:26 to 14:48 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948783
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-04-26 from 12:20 to 12:47 during MO-SAiC leg 3	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948794
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2020-02-15 from 11:05 to 11:20 during MO-SAiC leg 2	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948760
Energy dissipation rate profiles derived from tethered balloon-borne measurements on 2019-12-06 from 18:58 to 19:18 during MO-SAiC leg 1	Akansu, Elisa F; Siebert, Holger; Dahlke, Sandro; Graeser, Jürgen; Jaiser, Ralf; Sommerfeld, Anja	2022-09-22	948726
ac3airborne - flight-phase-separation	Risse, Nils; Marrollo, Giancarlo; Paul, Daria; Mech, Mario	2022-11-08	link
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature maps with 5 m resolution during the MOSAiC expedition, NetCDF format, version 3	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-11-14	950675
Helicopter-borne thermal infrared sea ice surface temperature maps with 1 m resolution during the MOSAiC expedition, NetCDF format, version 3	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Hendricks, Stefan; Jutila, Arttu; Ricker, Robert; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-11-14	950683
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Lead classification maps from helicopter-borne surface temperatures during the MOSAiC expedition	Thielke, Linda; Huntemann, Marcus; Spreen, Gunnar	2022-12-07	951569
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